

NIR spectroscopy-based determination of carotenoids content in ice cream supplemented with carrot lyophilized extract

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The interest of the food industry in the development of new products is constantly increasing and becoming more challenging due to consumers' awareness about healthier foods. Dairy products, such as ice creams and yogurts, are considered nutritious foods and present a great potential to incorporate bioactives (Rizk et al., 2014). The use of natural compounds as carotenoids in ice creams would be advantageous for the possible benefits to health due to their antioxidant characteristics and pro-vitamin A activity. Moreover, it could become an innovative superfood (Rajarajan et al., 2019). The objective of the research work was aimed to develop a carotenoids supplemented ice cream through addition of carrots' lyophilized extract before creaming phase and test the shelf-life of the product, knowing the low stability of carotenoids exposed to light and air. Extraction of carotenoids from fat matrices for traditional wet chemical analysis involves time-consuming and laborious procedures, especially because in carrot extract some components are highly lipophilic while others are soluble in water. NIR spectroscopy can represent a fast and non-destructive alternative for measuring carotenoids content in supplemented vanilla ice cream. Calibration has been built, collecting spectra of samples added of known amounts of carrot extract in the range 0-6 mg/L of carotenoids ($R^2=0.8813$; $SEC=0.6944$). External validation has been carried out with ice cream samples added with 4 mg/L of carotenoids and left in the shop for 48 hours, sampling at 6-hour intervals. From NIR results, it was evident that carotenoids maintained the initial concentration up to 24 hours before showing a slight decrease, but above the recommended daily dose.

Keywords: supplemented ice cream, carotenoids, antioxidant activity

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